

Acharya Vinoba Bhave and Bhoodan Movement

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Summary:

Vinayak Narahari Bhave, also known as Vinoba Bhave 11 September 1895 – 15 November 1982, was an Indian advocate of non violence and human rights. Often called Acharya (Teacher in Sanskrit), he is best known for the Bhoodan Movement. He is considered as National Teacher of India and the spiritual successor of Mahatma Gandhi. He was an eminent philosopher. The Gita has been translated into the Marathi language by him with the title Geetai (meaning 'Mother Gita' in Marathi). He was associated with Mahatma Gandhi in the Indian independence movement. He stayed for some time at Gandhi's Sabarmati ashram in a cottage that was named after him, 'Vinoba Kutir'. He gave talks on the Bhagavad Gita in Marathi to his fellow ashramites. These were later published in book form, as Talks on the Gita, and it has been translated into many languages both in India and elsewhere. Bhave felt that the source of these talks was something from above and he believed that its influence would endure even if his other works were forgotten. In the year 1940, he was chosen by Gandhi to be the first individual Satyagrahi. It is said that Gandhi envied and respected Bhave's celibacy, a vow he made in his adolescence, in fitting with his belief in the Brahmacharya principle. Bhave also participated in the Quit India Movement.

Keywords : Sarvodaya, Bhoodan, Equality, Non-violence, Gandhian Philosophy

Introduction:

Mother India has its glory that was completely achieved by ancient sages and their wisdom. It was flowing from one generation to another. Great saints and philosophers like Sankara, Ramanuja, Madhav, Ramakrishna, Vivekananda, Aurobindo, R.N.Tagore, Mahatma Gandhi and Vinoba Bhave, all of them under one roof of men who had with their religious, philosophical, ethical, intellectual and spiritual capacities enriched the glory of our country. But, when an individual observes them based on their role he would realize that they have conveyed to the society what they had spiritually and philosophically gained.¹

Subject Matter:

According to certain intellectuals, Vinoba Bhave was one of the most outstanding revolutionary mentors India has ever produced. According to Vinoba Bhave, Nehru was Mahatma Gandhi's political heir and Vinobaji was Mahatma Gandhi's spiritual heir.² Vinoba Bhave was a great social reformer and ethical force in the Indian ancient tradition interpreted for the sake of men and the spiritual welfare of modern society. His entire life was devoted to serving the people.

The national teacher of India, Vinoba had been recognized by Mahatma Gandhi as the first individual Satyagrahee for his devoted service to the people. He was a dedicated participant in the numerous movements and social activities started by Gandhi. After Mahatma Gandhi, this saint, social reformer, and spiritual leader, Vinoba Bhave launched a socio-economic and cultural revolution with the motto of Satyagraha, Ahimsa and Love to establish a casteless and classless society with social justice for all in Post-independence India. This

celibate leader considered Gandhi as a guide and philosopher but he never imitated him like a blind follower. Rather, he may be called a practitioner of Gandhian Philosophy. Gandhiji's concept of Trusteeship was practiced into action by his ardent follower Acharya Vinoba Bhave like an ever-free soul. He dedicated his life to starting the Bhoodan and Gramdan movement. Mahatma Gandhi had considered Vinoba as his spiritual heir. The job of converting the Sarvodaya philosophy into a plan of action was taken by Vinoba in the name of the Bhoodan Movement. The reason for starting the Bhoodan movement was a violent struggle between the landlords and the landless for land. Under the leadership of Vinoba Bhave, Akhil Bharatiya Sarva Seva Sangh accepted the challenges to translate into reality the objectives of the Sarvodaya philosophy. The basic aim of the Bhoodan had been to inspire the people to develop a selfless attitude and feelings for the good of the masses.

Vinoba Bhave had declared almost in the same spirit as Gandhi, that he should not follow blindly even the words of the Vedas greatest good of the greatest number. It gave birth to problems of minority and majority; it believed that to protect the interest of many, the interest of the few could be violated. This was very harmful because it might do injustice to the minority. Moreover, in this principle, we were not sure that those in the majority have realized the truth. Even one person might have realized the Truth. And in the name of the majority, we had no right to suppress that lone voice.

To eliminate this drawback, Mahatma Gandhi said that Sarvodaya meant the welfare of all. It did not mean the welfare of the few. Sarvodaya ideology encouraged the indivisible unity of life. It

refuses to divide life into opposite categories like individual versus state, national versus international, secular versus religious, individual salvation versus social progress. Individual development is good for society. The idea of Sarvodaya, as preached by the Geeta stood for merging one's interest in the interest of the society. Indeed, self-less action, keeping faith in truth and nonviolence, and the continued spiritual development of the individual was the goal of Sarvodaya.

Vinayak Narahari Bhave was born on 11 September 1895 in a small village called Gagoji (present-day Gagode Budruk) in Kolaba in the Konkan region of what is now Maharashtra. Vinayaka was the eldest son of Narahari Shambhu Rao and Rukmani Devi. The couple had five children; four sons named Vinayaka (affectionately called Vinya), Balakrishna, Shivaji and Dattatreya, and one daughter. His father was a trained weaver with a modern rationalist outlook and worked in Baroda. Vinayaka was brought up by his grandfather, Shamburao Bhave and was greatly influenced by his mother Rukmini Devi, a religious woman from Karnataka. Vinayaka was highly inspired after reading the Bhagavad Gita, at a very young age.⁴

A report in the newspapers about Gandhi's speech at the newly founded Banaras Hindu University attracted Bhave's attention. In 1916, after reading a newspaper piece by Mahatma Gandhi, Bhave threw his school and college certificates into a fire on his way to Bombay to appear for the intermediate examination. He wrote a letter to Gandhi and after an exchange of letters, Gandhi advised Bhave to come for a personal meeting at Kochrab Ashram in Ahmedabad. Bhave met Gandhi on 7 June 1916 and subsequently abandoned his studies. Bhave participated with a keen interest in the activities at Gandhi's ashram, like teaching, studying, spinning and improving the lives of the community. His involvement with Gandhi's constructive programmes related to Khadi, village industries, new education, sanitation and hygiene also kept on increasing.

Bhave went to Wardha on 8 April 1921 to take charge of the Ashram as desired by Gandhi. In 1923, he brought out Maharashtra Dharma, a Marathi monthly which had his essays on the Upanishads. Later on, this monthly became a weekly and continued for three years. In 1925, Gandhi sent him to Vaikom, Kerala to supervise the entry of the Harijans to the temple.

Bhave was arrested several times during the 1920s and 1930s and served a five-year jail sentence in the 1940s for leading non-violent resistance to British rule. The jails for Bhave had become the places of reading and writing. He wrote 'Ishavasyavritti' and 'Sthitaprajna Darshan' in jail. He also learnt four South Indian languages and

created the script of Lok Nagari at Vellore jail. In the jails, he gave a series of talks on the Bhagavad Gita in Marathi, to his fellow prisoners. Bhave participated in the nationwide civil disobedience periodically conducted against the British and was imprisoned with other nationalists. Despite these many activities, he was not well known to the public. He gained national prominence when Gandhi chose him as the first participant in a new nonviolent campaign in 1940. All were calling him by his short name, Vinoba. Bhave's younger brother Balkrishna was also a Gandhian. Gandhi entrusted him and Manibhai Desai to set up a nature therapy ashram at Urali Kanchan where Balkrishna spent all his life.⁵

Acharya Vinoba Bhave conveyed his attitude on the concept of Sarvodaya, "We desire the welfare of all, and also our own. But the question is as to which of them we give priority. If we give it to the good of others, our attitude is that of Sarvodaya. If it is otherwise, then it is not." As the ardent followers of Gandhiji, Vinoba executed the philosophy of Sarvodaya through non-violent means after Gandhiji. Vinoba Bhave advocated that the term Sarvodaya indicates a two-fold meaning. Firstly, Sarvodaya means making happiness for all by removing social dogmas and discriminations and secondly, establishing a new society with equality, divinity and kindness.⁶

According to Vinoba Bhave, 'The concept of Sarvodaya as preached by the Geeta is to merge oneself in the good of all'.⁷ It attempts to boost the human mind with ethical ideas. The concept of Sarvodaya and Vinoba are synonyms. Vinoba Bhave considers that Sarvodaya as the "Best dharma" (righteous living) and sarvodayamidam Tirtham (Universal blessing). The core meaning of all religions of the world, propose the well-being, prosperity and happiness of all human beings. In this way, Sarvodaya connects all the religions of the world.⁹ According to Vinoba Bhave, Sarvodaya is to establish based on the truth and non-violence, a classless and casteless society. In this society, everyone will get equal opportunities for their highest development. Indeed, Sarvodaya is a way to implement socialism in society. It was a great gift of Gandhian philosophy. Vinoba tried to eliminate the contemporary ruling system based on exploitation and discrimination. The concept of Sarvodaya was a strong weapon to solve the problems of Indian society. Vinoba stated that the means for Sarvodaya is the strength of masses, contrary violence and punishment. Sarvodaya can establish people's rights with the organization of mass strength from unjust rules.¹⁰ For the establishment of Sarvodaya society, Vinoba launched a lot of movement in a non-violent way. After Gandhi's assassination on 30th January 1948 all eyes were fixed upon on Vinoba to fulfill dreams of Mahatma Gandhi. He

proposed the formation of Sarvodaya Samaj to work for Gandhian thought.

As the ultimate ideal of Sarvodaya, Vinoba conceived of a society free from government. This did not imply that there would be no order. There would be order and government, but its authority would be distributed among villages. People living in such a social order would obey the moral laws of their own accord. Such a society would be a self-governing one. Vinoba wanted to do away with the government by politicians and replace it with a government of the people, based on love, compassion, and equality. Decisions here would be not taken by the majority, but by unanimous consent; and they would be carried out by the united strength of the ordinary people of the village. He visualized the progressive transformation of the society through minimum government to no government.

'Bhoodan' (Land-Gift) is the first step towards the establishment of the Sarvodaya Society. India a predominantly agricultural country had the enormous problem of landless peasants. Under the zamindari system, large-scale land holdings were being held by big landlords. While the farmers worked on the land and created the wealth they could not enjoy it. There was a movement called land to the tiller undertaken by the communists in Telangana. The deep economic disparities between landlords and peasants were creating a type of civil-war situation. Vinoba took up the issue and sought to give a Gandhian approach to the solution of the problem. The land ultimately belonged to God. Under certain circumstances, there had been unequal holdings. So something is required to level the holdings. But it will not be based on the violence of landless peasants against landlords and taking over the lands with force. But it is an attempt to appeal to the good nature of landowners to spare something for the landless.

According to Vinoba Bhave we should always look below what makes us happy if we look above, we feel unhappy. The idea of "Thy need is greater than mine" fills us with a sense of sacrifice. The second reason is to make people develop a sense of detachment. As we must give water to the thirsty so also we must give land to the tiller who demands. He wanted to bring home to the people all that land as it belongs to God. Today both rich and poor suffer from the ownership Complex. he wanted everyone should get free of any attachment. Thirdly when poor people start donating their land, it would have a moral impact on the rich. They should feel their moral responsibility to society. The Bhoodan movement was started by Saint Vinoba in the Telangana area through the spiritual transformation of the attitude of the rich men. His technique was love and truth. At Pochampalli village, in the Nalgonda district, where Vinoba toured, and keep a

question to Dalits. Giving land to landless Dalits would be the solution. Then Vinoba asked the people gathered if anybody is willing to donate surplus land and immediately a person came forward. This made Vinoba pursue the idea of Bhoodan. This idea of voluntary donation of land by the rich has been criticized by communists. They argue that most of the land donated by the rich peasant is uncultivable.

The idea of Bhoodan was based on the concept of partyless democracy. Vinoba stated, "In a sense, Bhoodan is itself an intensely and deeply political movement. A movement that aims so utterly to revolutionize man and society cannot be but political. But it is politics of kind I have described above-nor the politics of parties, elections, parliaments, and governments; but politics of the people-not Rajniti but Lokniti".¹¹ Bhoodan doesn't target only at collecting land from the people and disturbing it among the landless it tries to eliminate the gap between the rich and poor people through non-violent ways of truth and non-violence, love and cooperation should be the core principles governing individual and social behavior equality and social justice should be the main objective. To quote Jaya Prakash Narayan about Bhoodan, it stood for a society which would strive for the good of all, and in which everybody would be happy. In such a society there should no distinction between high and low. Justice and equality would form their distinguishing features and exploitation in any form be eliminated.¹²

The concept of Dan does't mean charity because the feeling of charity is against the spirit of equality and brotherhood. According to Jayaprakash Narayan bhoodan is not a charity movement, behind it is Mahatma Gandhi's thought of trusteeship concept. Vinoba Bhave realized that the Gandhian way must be fruitful to eliminate inequality in the society. So, he devoted himself to complete the opportunity of the land gift movement to help the landless.

On 18th April 1951, Vinoba received 100 acres of donation of land at the village of Pochampalli in Telengana from Ramchandra Reddy, a local landlord. He realized the possibility of a great revolution with love and non-violence. He started every action to change the heart of the people to do something for landless and poor people. Vinoba was able to collect 12,200 acres of land as a gift in just 51 days from the starting day. Bhoodan was the pragmatic way to meet the problems of acute poverty and unemployment. During this movement, Vinoba focused that hungry people will not tolerate their suffering anymore; land and wealth must be redistributed.¹³ The cruelties of capitalism can be eliminated by receiving land as a donation from landlords by the change of heart. Vinoba walked thousand by

thousand miles for looting land by love for the rise of all. Vinoba realized the power of the Padayatra (March on foot). He walked for 13 years throughout India to bring a socio-economic change for landless and poor people. Vinoba left Panuar on 12th September 1951 and returned on 10th April 1964. He started Toofan Yatra, using a vehicle in Bihar for almost four years. He addressed thousands of meetings and mobilized the people to ignore the barriers of caste, color, class and religion. From the notorious Chambal Valley, a gang of dacoit surrendered themselves to Vinoba in May 1960. For saint Vinoba, it was a victory of non-violence in Post-Independence India.¹⁴

The Bhoodan Movement has been weak on the publicity front there are not journals and books on the subject to spread the message of the movement. Sufficient information was not available about the development work done by the Bhoodan. Lack of facts and figures in detail regarding development work done makes it difficult to describe an overall assessment. Bhoodan was a mass movement and the people themselves who should be organized, the Samiti was dissolved. Therefore, the Bhoodan movement has not been able to cover the imagination of the masses as it was expected of it. The slow-moving legislative institutions should be geared up. The farmers who had donated the land were forced to pay the revenue for land given away by them. Because of the time-consuming process involved in making the transfer legal, this made their donors taking back land from tenants earlier given by them.¹⁵

Conclusion:

Vinoba was greatly influenced by the Bhagvad Gita and his thoughts and efforts were based upon the doctrines of the Holy Book. He set up a number of Ashrams to promote a simple way of life, devoid of luxuries that took away one's focus from the Divine. He established the Brahma Vidya Mandir in 1959, a small community for women, aiming at self-sufficiency on the lines of Mahatma Gandhi's teachings. He took a strong stand on cow slaughter and declared to go on fast until it was banned in India. In November 1982, Vinoba Bhave fell seriously ill and decided to end his life. He refused to accept any food and medicine during his last days. On 15 November 1982, the great social reformer passed away. Vinoba Bhave was the first international figure to receive the Ramon Magsaysay Award in 1958. He was awarded Bharat Ratna posthumously in 1983.

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